

POLITICAL EUPHEMISMS AS A CROSS-CULTURAL PHENOMENON FUNCTIONS IN THE COVERAGE OF MILITARY ACTIONS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK NEWSPAPERS

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Abstract: *This study examines the linguistic and cultural features of political euphemisms in English and Uzbek language print media, with a particular focus on the coverage of military conflicts. Political euphemisms are a key element of media discourse, shaping public opinion and influencing the perception of war and security. Each euphemism reflects national and cultural characteristics, and the choice of expressions is determined by societal values and norms. Comparative analysis shows that, while euphemisms in the American media serve to rationalise and control public perception, those in the Uzbek media strengthen patriotism and trust in state institutions. Therefore, political euphemisms are not only a means of softening speech, but also an important ideological tool for shaping society's attitude towards war and military action.*

Key words: *euphemism, culture, political, military action, patriotism, public perception. American and Uzbek newspapers.*

Analysing the linguistic and cultural features of political euphemisms in English- and Uzbek-language print media provides insight into how language shapes public opinion and the interpretation of events. Political speech and writing are largely the defence of the indefensible ... political language has to consist largely of euphemism, question-begging and sheer cloudy vagueness (George Orwell, *Politics and the English Language*). Each euphemism reflects national and cultural specifics, and the choice of polite expressions is determined by the values and norms of a particular society. The problem of comparing political euphemisms in different languages remains relevant. In particular, a comparison of American and Uzbek cultures reveals contrasting priorities in how the two cultures cover military actions.

The aim of this study is to examine political euphemisms in American and Uzbek newspaper texts as a reflection of cultural values, focusing on the opposition between the coverage of military actions and conflicts.

In English language newspapers typically use euphemisms in covering military conflicts to align with political discourse, maintain national interest, and control public perception. Moreover, euphemisms are employed in English-language media to soften

the perception of violence and military setbacks. For example, “*The assassination spread some fear among Russia’s military and political elites. It also **eliminated a top military leader** who, according to Ukraine, had ordered the use of banned chemical substances*” (*The New York Times*, 2024, December 19). The euphemism “*eliminated*” is a verb meaning “*removed*” that is often used in military rhetoric. It softens the perception of violent death, making it part of a strategic necessity. In official reports, it is used to refer to the death of an enemy without mentioning specific actions, such as murder or assault. This euphemism is particularly common in political and military rhetoric in the English-language media. If the killing of a military leader is presented as “*eliminated*”, it is perceived as part of a strategy rather than a crime. In different contexts, it can be found in reports on special operations, counter-terrorism measures, and political assassinations.

“... *help Ukraine’s forces on the battlefield, who are **steadily losing ground**, my colleague Michael Schwirtz writes*” (*The New York Times*, 2024, December 19).

The euphemistic expression “*steadily losing ground*” describes the process of gradual retreat or loss of control over territory. It is used to describe Ukraine's military defeats, instead of the more direct “*losing territory*”. The euphemism softens the defeat and destruction of positions, and indicates a gradual loss of influence, showing the situation as controllable.

In Uzbek language newspapers, euphemisms are used to describe military actions, weapons, and defence strategies. In this sphere, euphemisms are used to maintain patriotic sentiment, strengthen trust in the army, and justify its role in society. For instance, «*Ҳозир йигитларимиз учун **ҳарбий соҳада хизмат қилиш нафақат бурч, балки шон-шараф** ишига айланди*» (*Янги Ўзбекистон*, 2024, 5 январь, Б.2). This euphemistic expression is an example of political rhetoric aimed at creating a positive image of the armed forces and strengthening patriotic sentiments. It is also used to smooth over negative or controversial aspects of military service and to create a more positive image of the army. “*Military service is not just a duty, it is an honour and a privilege*” extols military service, presenting it as honourable and prestigious. This creates a positive image of the army and encourages young people to serve in the armed forces.

«*Миллий армиямизнинг ташкилий тузилмаларини такомиллаштириши бўйича чора-тадбирлар **қўшинларнинг жанговар тайёргарлиги, ҳарбий қудрати ва салоҳиятини янада ошириши имконини берди***» (*Янги Ўзбекистон*, 2024, 5 январь, Б.2). This excerpt contains several euphemisms that indicate an increase in military power. The terms «*жанговар тайёргарлиги, ҳарбий қудрати* and *салоҳиятини*» sound positive and inspire respect, while concealing the possible negative consequences of an arms race. Patriotism permeates the entire text,

emphasising the importance of love for the Motherland and readiness to defend its interests. Traditional values prevail, with an emphasis on collective values such as national unity and defence of the Motherland.

Euphemisms related to the military sphere in the Uzbek media have specific characteristics that help soften the perception of military events and operations. In such cases, the vocabulary emphasises the defensive and peaceful nature of any military activity, presenting it as a necessary step to ensure peace and security, rather than aggression. They are aimed at creating a positive, protective image of military action in the context of national security.

To conclude, the analysis of political euphemisms in American and Uzbek newspapers demonstrates how language serves as both a communicative tool and an ideological instrument in the coverage of military conflicts. In American media, euphemisms depersonalize violence, rationalize military actions, and frame them as strategic necessities rather than human tragedies. This reflects the broader cultural orientation toward individualism and the maintenance of national interest. In contrast, Uzbek media employ euphemisms that emphasize patriotism, unity, and the honour of military service.

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